

TEACHING STRATEGIES AND ASSESSMENT METHODS FOR ONLINE PHARMACY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness in terms of knowledge change pre- and post-online learning and to explore Malaysian pharmacy students' perception and acceptance of online learning. An independent web-based learning module was developed for a module on basic patient counselling skills for pharmacy students of a Pharmaceutical education and research institute. Out of a total of 60 students, 57 (96.8%) students participated in the study and completed an assessment and feedback survey. Students' knowledge scores were found to have significantly improved after completing the online learning activity. Overall, more than 90% of students agreed that the online module was useful for new topic learning and revising, provided relevant content, which was arranged in a clear and logical manner, and thus facilitated their understanding. The majority of students reported to have enjoyed and satisfied with the online learning. More than half of them agreed that online learning was time-saving, allowed self-paced learning and improved their confidence level.

Keywords: e-Learning, Patient Counselling, Knowledge Assessment, Perception

In the educational system, effective teaching and learning activities are critical for supporting students' learning. Given current technology breakthroughs, the traditional classroom and textbooks are no longer the primary medium of knowledge transfer. Online learning (or e-learning) with classes delivered entirely via the internet or blended learning (which combines classes delivered virtually via the internet and periodic face-to-face meetings in a traditional classroom) is now widely used for teaching and learning in tertiary educational institutions because it offers

several advantages over didactic lectures (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015). Online learning is a general word for learning that occurs via the internet, whereas e-learning is described as a learning process that involves the use of electronic media or devices as tools for supporting learning. Furthermore, this modern application of learning pedagogy has enabled course contents to reach broader audiences around the world (Means et al., 2013), with online e-learning platforms such as Future Learn, Coursera, Udacity, Alison, and recording millions of global learners registering for online courses offered by top universities (Bendezu-Quispe et al., 2017). Importantly, it may cut educational costs for both the school and students because the utilization of interactive web-based courses to supplement traditional curriculum on campus can serve to efficiently offer educational programs to students (Casement, 2013).

Methods

Development and implementation of the online learning module

The module content was created in accordance with the syllabus of a three-year Diploma of Pharmacy program. Basic patient counselling, which is one of the lecture subjects of the 'Hospital Pharmacy' unit, was chosen at the commencement of constructing the online module because it is the primary work obligation of the pharmacy profession. The website solution (wordwallnet.com) was used to create the website (www.quizalize.com) that houses this online learning module. The following key subtopics were covered: basic concepts of pharmacological care, an introduction to patient counselling, including its objectives, systematic techniques to counselling, and essential information to advise patients. The most regularly used medicine delivery devices, such as inhalers and insulin injection, were chosen and displayed utilizing video clips to demonstrate techniques/steps of giving insulin and using inhalers.

Data collection

To assess the efficiency of the online module, an 18-item multiple-choice questionnaire based on the course syllabus was created to assess students' knowledge

before and after the online learning activity. Five pharmacy seminars who are also registered pharmacists content evaluated all questions. To decrease the possibility of bias, the identical questions were utilized as a post-test. The findings were utilized to measure any knowledge gain attributed to participation in this online learning. Prior to the online learning activity, all participants in a class were given a knowledge exam. Following the completion of the baseline knowledge test, granting students access to the constructed online module was put on the university student web-portal and the IPER pharmacy student society's social media webpage.

For a period of two weeks, students got access to the website. They could examine the website content as many times as they wanted, at their own pace, at any time and from any location. After two weeks, a knowledge post-test was administered in class to eliminate any information exchange among students and to ensure that this was the individual's best effort. Aside from assessing post-test knowledge, the instructor prepared a role-play session in which each student had to perform medication counselling and use a medical device (insulin injection pen or inhaler) based on a prescription given in a laboratory session. The instructor provided comments to the students, and their counselling abilities were graded based on the presentation of knowledge or procedures for administering drugs and medical devices. The total score could range from 56 (the lowest possible score) to 100 (the highest possible score).

Results

Students' knowledge scores

The knowledge assessments were completed by 60 students (96.8%) of the 57 students that registered for the course and participated in the online learning. Students' knowledge mean (standard deviation, SD) scores in the pre- and post-tests were 8.9 (1.85) and 13.11 (1.78), respectively, representing a 4.2 (2.23) increase ($p < 0.001$). The role play session was completed by all students with a mean score of 6.79 1.08.

Discussion

The objective of this study is to validate the use of online learning in undergraduate pharmacy education by reporting on online learning acceptability and knowledge generation using empirical data. Following their brief participation in the online learning exercise, there was a discernible improvement in the students' mean knowledge scores. This indicated that the online resources were successful in enhancing the knowledge and patient counseling abilities of the students. The results corroborated those of earlier studies showing that e-learning is a useful tool for enhancing student understanding in pharmacy. (Cook et al., 2008; Salter et al., 2014; Williams, 2014).

Since the majority of the students registered in the course took part in the study, it is safe to infer that the participants are representative of the group of students taking the course. Even though this was the course's first attempt at online learning, the feedback on the experience was overwhelmingly positive. Similar to other research evaluating how learners see applications for online learning (Nesterowicz, Librowski & Edelbring, 2014; Azhari, Ming & Khan, 2015),

Most people found the online learning activities to be enjoyable and satisfactory, and most expressed a desire to keep learning online. Students also noted that the website made it easier for them to complete the quizzes, which enabled them to identify their knowledge gaps and stoked their interest in the subject after utilizing the website. The study is in line with the widespread trend of using web-based learning as a practical tool to boost students' self-assurance in their skills and knowledge. This was in line with earlier research showing the value of e-learning and how it might boost students' self-esteem (Hassali et al., 2012; Ruehter et al., 2012).

To help students develop their knowledge and skills effectively, a variety of teaching strategies, including active instructional approaches like class discussions, problem-based learning, role playing, and game-based learning, have been used in the classroom. In spite of this, technological advancements have led to numerous new methods of teaching students. Information technology advancements have

changed the way that pharmacy is taught in higher institutions, moving away from the conventional didactic lecture model and toward web-based virtual learning (Azhari & Ming, 2015). Technology-based instructional aids are developing quickly, and the internet has taken over as the primary information source. Students have made substantial use of technology that supports digital learning, such as learning management systems and mobile applications.

According to earlier research, students frequently use social networking sites for educational purposes (Benetoli, Chen, & Aslani, 2015). It's possible that students in this study used digital learning tools more frequently than they did books or textbooks. Similar to this, a survey conducted at another local institution discovered that the majority of students favor using electronic books, including e-versions of textbooks and reference materials (Roesnita & Zainab, 2013). A different study found that medical students strongly preferred mobile learning (Han, Nelson & Wetter, 2014). When creating academic curriculum, it is crucial to take students' learning preferences into account in order to maximize teaching and learning processes. Depending on the sorts of subjects and students, different teaching styles may be most suited for pharmacy education. While pharmacy practice may prefer a different strategy, such as a blended learning or flipped classroom approach and laboratory sessions, many basic pharmacy disciplines are lecture-based in the classroom (Ruehter et al., 2012; Wong et al., 2014). The issue of a seamless access to the network is a concern in our local tertiary institutions even though online learning could improve students' performance. Slow connection speeds in the university grounds may deter students from studying online. It is hopeful that improvements to the internet connection and coverage would result from the Malaysian government's initiative to expand broadband connection speed in campus networks.

Conclusion

The effectiveness and acceptance of online learning as a support tool for the Hospital Pharmacy course were confirmed by preliminary study data. It was

determined that this module significantly improved the knowledge of the pupils on the subject under consideration. Further supporting the website's value as a teaching tool for students was the high degree of pleasure and enjoyable experience linked to the online learning activity seen in this study. Before results of online learning are compared to those of traditional lectures in the future, the website, its content, and its format may be improved depending on feedback from students. This platform may also make it simple to integrate social media sites like Twitter and Facebook in order to support shifting educational trends and boost learners' engagement and satisfaction.

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